

ISic3219

I.Sicily inscription 3219

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Taylor Bennett,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 608

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. d(is) m(anibus) [s(acrum)]

2. Arria[---]

3. vix(it) [ann(is)]

4. XLV[---]

5. Arriu[sEpityn]

6. chan[us][---][f(ecit)]

Apparatus

Text from Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Sacred to the shades of the underworld. Arria lived [c. 45-49] years. Arrius [Epityn]chanus made (this).

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285110

EDR 121187
EDCS 14800600

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 06.1239 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 60

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